

Sample ID **3-5 (Combined)**

Operator ID **user**

Notes

Elapsed Time	00:01:00
Median Diam.	144.3 nm
Mean Diam.	173.6 nm
Polydispersity	0.447
GSD	1.837

Lognormal Size Distribution

d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)	d(nm)	G(d)	C(d)
53.1	26	5	123.8	97	40	217.5	80	75
66.2	44	10	133.7	99	45	240.8	70	80
76.9	58	15	144.3	100	50	271.0	58	85
86.5	70	20	155.8	99	55	314.7	44	90
95.8	80	25	168.3	97	60	392.5	26	95
104.9	87	30	182.4	93	65			
114.2	93	35	198.5	87	70			